
“ENVIRONMENTAL CONCERNS OF DELHI CITY”

Anil Kapur¹, Dr. Amitabh Bhargava² and Dr. Sumit Agarwa³

¹Ph.D. Scholar- Amity Business School, Greater Noida.

²Professor, Amity Business School, Greater Noida.

³External Co- IIMT University, Faridabad.

ABSTRACT

In the present study the scholar has analyzed factors that are changing the ecology of Delhi a historical city of rulers and ancient monuments into an urban city full of action crowding and environmental hazards to an extent that it has become unlivable for the habitants of the city. The scholar has suggested certain short and long term measures that may speed up the pace of reforms being undertaken by the City Administration to reverse this life threatening environmental degeneration.

Keywords: Road congestions, environmental degeneration, pollutants,

INTRODUCTION

Delhi is a landlocked City in Northern India with limited resources in comparison to growing population. It became Indian Empire in 1911. The population of the city rose from 2.38 lacs in 1911 to 6.96 lacs in 1947.

Following the partition of India in 1947, Delhi's flourishing service economy and high per capita income attracted migrants from across the newly laid borders leading to sharp surge in the population. Delhi's population continue to grow from 6.96 lacs in 1947 to 14.30 lacs in 1951 , 84.20 lacs by 1991, to 1.10crores by 2011and to 2.32 crores by 2024which is more than 30 fold increase since independence. The population of Delhi is still on the rise and is expected to touch anything between 2.55 crores to 2.98 crores by the end of year 2031. Continuous migration of people from other states has put a lot of pressure on housing in Delhi.

Population density of capital has grown up from 2742 per sq. km. in 1971 to 14491now and is significantly higher than the national average of 382 per square km. and temping citizens to resort to illegal extensions in their houses to accommodate more and more people.

Rapid Urbanization of Delhi along with growth in economic activities in its surrounding areas, over-crowding of human habitats and lack of discipline in the accomplishment of industrial activities has led us to a number of environmental issues such as air, water & noise pollution, loss of biodiversity. Besides this, hazardous waste are causing serious threat to the environment.

Delhi has a number of monuments of tourist interest in the city such as Lal Quila, Jama Masjid, Qutub Minar, Nizamuddin Dargah.

There are some very popular whole-sale trade markets such as Chandni Chowk, Sadar bazar, Karol bagh, and Nehru Place. All these places of interest are visited by lacs of domestic & international tourists and traders of bordering states. Besides this Supreme Court of India, Parliament House , Ministerial head offices and buildings, Corporate Offices of renowned industrial establishments are other important sites that are frequently visited by people of various states of India and all this mount additional burden on already burdened Transport and civic services of the city.

Despite of big expansion of Metro Rail network taking place during the last two decades, and expansion of roads, construction of bridges and elevated corridors and bypasses, Delhi’s suburb remains highly congested throughout the day and face extended traffic peak hours starting from 8 am till 8 pm. This virtually leaves no time for residents of Delhi to enjoy a noise free, pollution free joy ride in the city with their families. Emergency services also remain crippled throughout the day and a lot of productive public time and fuel energy is wasted on the roads. It is a recurring loss of national resources and a big source of pollution in the city.

Environmental issues mainly related to natural resources such as air, water, soil and afforestation. Air is a vital nutrient as we get 90% of our energy from it. One breathes around 10000 liters of air every day. Our lungs are designed for cleaner air, but when they encounter harmful elements in the air such as nitrogen dioxide, Sulphur dioxide, ozone and microscopic particulate matters the same get absorbed into our blood stream overtime and get deposited in various organs, increasing the risk of respiratory, cardiovascular and neurological complications.

According to Centre for Science and environment 51% of city’s daily emissions are contributed by motor vehicles and city’s Pollution levels are amongst the highest in India.

Contribution of different sources of PM 2.5 levels in the city is depicted as under:-

DIAGRAM –1

(Source: TIMES OF INDIA’s article of 7/11/2024

According to Central Pollution Board, PM 2.5 levels in the city oscillates between 209.5 to 290.5 micrograms per cubic meters against national standards of 60units and WHO’S standards of 15 units in 24hrs.

As per recent study of Energy Policy Institute of university of Chicago people of Delhi lose 8.2 years from their expected life due to these elevated pollution levels.

Research Objectives

In the urban context transportation becomes a serious issue as on the one hand it leads to heavy congestions, poor speed on roads, and on the other hand severally pollute the city environment. The main objectives of the research study therefore are:-

- a. To identify various factors that are causing environmental pollution
- b. To understand their impact on the lives of residents of Delhi
- c. To assess various short term and long term measures being undertaken by the city administration for bringing down and reversing the environmental degradations taking place.
- d. To suggest measures that can accelerate the speed of reforms being undertaken by the state administration in bringing down/reverse these environmental deteriorations in and around the Metropolis.

LITRATURE REVIEW

Existing studies at different platforms, do not correlate issues of environmental degeneration, congestion and chaos prevailing in the metro city of Delhi. Studies similar to proposed research work and issues covered by them are briefly discussed below:-

- i. **“Sentiment analysis of Air quality perception in major Metro cities of India”** an article in 14 ICCCNT IEEE conference in IIT- Delhi (July 6-8-2023) by kushagra Wadhwa and other team members of Department of Environmental Engineering, Delhi Technology University.

This study aimed to compare the sentiment analysis of air quality perception in two major metro cities, Delhi and Mumbai using natural language processing techniques. The results highlighted the need for targeted interventions to address the problem of air pollution in these cities.

- ii. **“Effect of Metro Expansions on Air Pollution in Delhi”** an article by Deepti Goel and Sonam Gupta published by Oxford University Press in 2015.

It analysed whether the Delhi Metro led to localised reduction in three transportation source pollutants CO₂, NO₂ and PM_{2.5} and found that there were reductions but for the short run.

- iii. **“The Importance of including Carcinogenic Benzene in real time ambient Air Quality Data in Delhi”** an article by Nancy Agarwal & Arushi Baboota of Computer Science and Engineering stream, IIT-DELHI in Net health workshop-2016. In this article relevance of tracking benzene based on its abundance in the Indian capital and its harmful impacts on human health and also identified challenges in monitoring it and its implementation solutions.

- iv. **“ Cost estimates for road congestions in Delhi- projections and recommendations”** an article by Harry Raymond Joseph ,Gaurav Raina and other members of Department Of Electrical Engineering ,IIT -MADRAS in Transportation System Workshop, COMSNETS 2015.

Preliminary investigation was carried out into the economic costs of congestion in Delhi. It was assessed that productivity loss dominates the overall economic costs.

- v. **“Air Quality Analysis & Prediction using Machine learning: Pune Smart City Case Study”** an article by Pranav Sonawane and other members of Dept. of Mechanical Engineering –Vishwakarma Institute of Information Technology 2023 –Pune in 2023 IEEE 8TH International conference in Technology.

This work deals with the pre-processing 1 year data ten analysis and visualisations are done using data analysis tools of Tableau and Machine Learning decisions tree algorithm. Data analysis provides the method

to predict the future air pollution levels so that preventive measures can be implemented by people as well as administration.

- vi. **“Effect of odd –even vehicular restrictions on ambient noise levels in Delhi city”** an article by N Garg ,A.k.Sinha, M.Dahiya and P.Kumar of CSIR -National Physical Laboratory , Central Pollution Control Board Delhi and National Institute of Technology, Kurukshetra.

The research paper describes the ambient noise data acquired in Delhi City under diversified National Ambient Noise Monitoring (NANMN) set up across seven major cities of India and covering 70 stations for continuous noise monitoring throughout the year.

- vii. **“Smart City Sustainable Development Modelling Through Quantitative Analysis of Air Pollutants : A study on Chennai ,India”** by Mohammed Firose K of Silberman College of Business ,New Jersey and Navita Mahajan, Deepa Gupta, Arshia Sharma, Anjan Gupta, Rahul Kumar and Shreya Rai of Amity International Business School –Noida.

The research paper focuses on conducting a predictive analysis of PM2.5 and PM10 levels in Chennai, India, to contribute to understanding air pollution management and sustainable development.

- viii. **“ECOSIMULATE : Pollution Mitigation and Simulation using AI-Driven Environmental Modelling”** an article by Soham Wagh and other members of SRM Institute of Science and Technology-Kattankulathur –Indian the 5th ICSCSA-2025.The above research work introduced a real time pollution monitoring and simulation platform that integrates live air quality data with a novel mitigation model base on artificial tree deployment. Using the Google Quality API , the system collects dynamic pollutant data including PM2.5 CARBON MONOXIDE (CO) and temperature from major India cities. The Project supports data driven urban planning and offers a scalable, research –friendly tool for environmental management and policy decision – making.

- ix. **“Exploring Misconceptions and challenges of Electric Vehicle adoption in India”** research work of Sitharthan Ramachandran and others, published in 2025, was supported by the Vellore Institute of Technology ,India. This paper aims explore the prevalent misconceptions related to electric vehicles in India, focusing on two primary aspects emissions and challenges.The study examines the lifecycle emissions, encompassing battery production, electricity generation, and disposal, to assess their environmental benefits comprehensively. Additionally the research identifies challenges hindering EV adoption in India.

- x. **“Enablers and barriers of Electric Vehicles in India: A Review”** an article by Hari Om Bansal and Praveen Goyal of Birla Institute of Technology and Science, Pilani, Rajasthan.

The Present Study discuss the need for electric vehicles in India and the technologies available in the market which can be implemented in the Indian scenario. The paper also discuss about the policy decisions taken by the government and investments made by Indian automotive makers in electric vehicle segment.

“A Survey of EV Charging Systems with Solar PV in India” an article by FAIZ Mohd. and Prof. Sainul Abdin Jaffery of Department of Electrical Engineering, Jamia Millia Islamia ,New Delhi’s , in 2025 IEEE DELCON –International conference on Recent Technologies in Engineering for Sustainable Development. In this paper discussion has been made about Electric Vehicles (EVs) despite numerous environmental and economic advantages, have not been widely adopted in India. It also explains why these issues are peculiar to the developing countries scenario.

xi. “Development and Evaluation of an Integrated Multi-Modal Transportation System – a case study of Delhi” An article by Ravi Sekhar Chahimuri ME, Ph.D. and others in Transport Journal (2018)

The primary objectives of this research revolve around understanding and evaluating Integrated Multi-Modal Urban Transportation (IMMTS) in the Indian context.

xii. “Review of Public Transportation Integration and modelling strategies: Towards seamless urban mobility” an article by Anjum M. Mirza and Rajesh Jain of Gujrat Technical University Ahmedabad (Online Publication of Sept. 27,2024). The primary aim of this study was to evaluate the integration between public transportation modes, specifically metro rail and buses, in Indian cities, with a focus on sustainability.

Materials and Methodology

In order to understand the impact of measure undertaken by the City Administration for reversing environmental deteriorations scholar has identified major projects undertaken in the past decades for decongestion of city’s roads and cleaning of environment such as setting up of Metro Rail Project; expansion metro rail system in and around the city area ; expansion of major roads and highways; Building of viaducts and bridges; Integration of Metro Rail system with other modes of transport; manufacture of economical clean fuel vehicle options and development of infrastructure for them; and analyzed the same with the aim of making suggestions that may represent the voice of the common residents of the city.

DATA ANALYSIS /DISCUSSION

Detailed analysis of steps taken by the State Government and the Civic Bodies in the past 20 years for correcting environmental issues of Delhi City are discussed below:

Firstly, Delhi Metro Rail, a Mass Rapid Transport System was planned in Delhi city with the primary aim of decongesting the roads of Delhi. Today, time saved by metro rail passengers’ accounts to 269 million hours per annum and also Metro operations achieve reduction in fuel consumption to the extent of 2,55,000Tones per annum. But, despite of rapid increase in the Metro Rail operations in the last two decades, there is no big relief from daily road congestions. This is evident from the following statistics:-

CHART-I

Growth of Metro Rail & Motor Vehicles in Delhi in the last 20 years

year	Metro track kms.	Metro cars under operation	Average daily commuters travelling Metro rail	Total lenth of Delhi’s roads (in Kms)	Number of motor cars registered in Delhi (in Lacs)
2002	8.2	32	25,000	28508	35.5
2007	73.36	240	4,60,000	NA	47.0
2011	196.66	844	16,60,000	31180	69.3

2019	357.23	2100	47,00,000	NA	112.0
-------------	---------------	-------------	------------------	-----------	--------------

(Source Google search of 12-03-2026)

These statistics clearly indicate that people of Delhi using Motor Vehicles and Metro Rail System are going up simultaneously and almost with the same pace and that a large section of society still prefer to use their personal road vehicles for commuting. Figures of yearly registration of motor vehicles during the last 07 years given below also point out this trend:

CHART -II

YEAR	No of new motor vehicles registered in Delhi
2018	726830
2019	641889
2020	424294
2021	458529
2022	608138
2023	657889
2024	711113
2025	816051
TOTAL	5992733

(Source: TIMES OF INDIA's article of 1/1/2026)

Thus even heavy resources deployed by the Central & State Governments in the implementation of a Mass Rapid Transport Project "Delhi Metro Rail" are not able to shift commuters of Delhi from the use of their private vehicles to Delhi Metro Rail system because the same is not yet offering seamless travel to all important locations of the city and there are last mile connectivity issues that still being attended by the State Government.

Surprisingly, private vehicles which account for more than 97% of the road vehicles running in the city are able to carry only 18% of daily commuters. On the other-hand Public Transport Buses which account for only 1.2% of the motor vehicles are able to carry more than 25% of daily commuters.

Secondly, another major source of PM 2.5 pollutants is coal based Thermal plants. Besides this, So₂ (Sulphur Dioxide) pollutants are also formed in the atmosphere due to burning of fossil fuel by these thermal power plant. America's environmental protection Agency (EPA) says high concentration of SO₂ can harm trees & plants by damaging foliage and decreasing growth, besides causing acid rain & smog. Delhi is also experiencing wind blowing dusty events during summer months that impact PM 10 particles which start oscillating between 347.8 to 439.8 micrograms per cubic meter against national standards of 100 microgram and WHO's standards of 45 micrograms. To control environmental impact of PM10 particles we require massive urban redevelopment needing large scale roadside plantations, grass cover on exposed areas and scientific vacuum cleaning of roads. Though vacuum cleaning of roads has been initiated in full swing, green cover and plantation shall form part of long term planning in years to come.

Thirdly, Delhi's Master Plans drawn by Delhi Development Authority (DDA), from time-to-time, permitted increase in the FAR (Floor Area Ratio) of residential plots to enable plot owners to construct additional floors and accommodate increasing population in the city. They have also been allowed public & semipublic activities from these residential areas such as guest houses, Path labs, schools, banks, Nursing homes and fitness centers. All these modifications in the rules have, however led to overburdening of city's civic utilities, roads and parking facilities already under great stress.

Fourthly, E-Rickshaws are working as a stopgap arrangement to provide last mile connectivity at certain Metro Stations but they create congestions, noise and safety risks for pedestrians and due to various limitations in design are not universally acceptable as last mile connectivity vehicles.

Fifthly, to date total 102 flyover have been built in Delhi city and 9 more are coming up at various busy locations to decongest traffic. Experts however warn that flyovers often provide temporary relief. They primarily provides more space for private vehicles. Initially, traffic may move a little faster, but soon more car appear on these roads and congestion returns back on these locations.

Sixthly, Delhi generate 11000 Metric tone of Municipal Solid waste (MSW), 548 Metric tone of electric waste and about 1100 Metric ton of plastic waste on daily basis which require very strict monitoring, management and recycling. The city administration is actively involved in their management and set targets for their utilization for energy generation, for manufacture of agriculture compost and recycled products. Government of India has also set year wise minimum targets for the producers to utilize recycled waste in construction from the Financial year 2026-27.

Finally, Yamuna, once a clean river, now overwhelms with its contaminated, dead water and stench. The main cause of Yamuna river contamination is the untreated sewage flowing to the Yamuna from the unauthorized colonies. City administration has constructed more reservoirs to block their direct flow into the river. Not only that 11 projects have been approved for the restoration of Yamuna flood plains on a total area of 1600 hectares of eastern and western banks of Yamuna. Progress on this front shall be visible only after a reasonable period of time.

The above discussions point out that the city administration is taking various short term/long term measures to reverse the environmental degeneration taking place. In some cases these are proving counter-productive and some other cases results can be known only after the whole process is completed.

New initiatives taken up

Government of NCT of Delhi have taken serious note of environmental deteriorations in the capital city and taken following new initiatives for speedy recovery:-

1. Closing of thermal power plants
2. Deployment of Mechanical Road Sweepers , Water Sprinklers and Anti- smog guns
3. Concessional Electric Vehicle Policy
4. Prohibition on open burning of garbage/dry leaves
5. Relocation of hazardous industrial units on the outskirts of city.
6. Immediate exit of BS-I, II, III complied motor vehicles and BS IV complied vehicles in 5 years.
7. Setting up of Unified Metropolitan Authority (DUMTA) for streamlining Public Transport system
8. Collaboration with University of Chicago Trust in India & IIT –Kanpur on reducing Delhi's in use vehicular emissions.
9. Drawing of plans to develop two city forests in the South West and North West of city
10. Allocation of Rupees 4391crores by the Central Government for the purchase of 14000 E- buses for Delhi city and Rupees 2000 crore for charging stations for these buses.

(Source : Times of India articles of 16/12/2025,24/12/2025, 1/1/2026,5/2/2026,7/02/2026)

Significance of the study

The City of Delhi which is also the capital of India is today in the grip of environmental pollutions, road congestions and chaos. It is therefore the prime responsibility of all the stake holders i.e. the government of India, the city administration and its residents to take collective action at war footing levels for early reversal of this life threatening environment and the above work of the scholar who is born and brought up in Delhi is dedicated towards strengthening the efforts of the Local Administration for bringing back clean and health environment in and around the city for which the factors affecting health environment of the city in the past decades have been analyzed and measures have been suggested which according to scholar can work simultaneously for bringing down pollutants and decongesting the city environment in a big way.

Recommendations

The scholar being born and brought up in Delhi and having worked with major transport organizations, namely Indian Railways and Delhi Metro Rail Corporation has taken up this research work to get associated with the efforts being made by the city administration in reversing environmental degeneration encircling the city of Delhi and from analyses of the material information collected suggest following short term & long term measures which according to him can speed up the pace of these reforms

- I. Government should laydown norms for running of zonal head offices/Zonal Offices of PSUs including banks and educational institutions in Delhi. There should be restrictions on the number of establishments and also number of officials operating in such establishments. This will reduce concentration of government establishments as well as accommodation needs of their employees thereby reduction in peak hour traffic on Delhi's roads, reduction in Government spending. Areas so vacated by these establishments can then be converted into green spaces & recreation areas for nearby residents.
- II. Hiring of Diesel, petrol & CNG driven cars by the Government Offices, PSUs, banks and educational institutions should be completely banned and they may be asked to hire vehicles using clean fuel options. Time frame can be decided for the enforcement of these norms.

- III. All government establishments, banks and other education institutions in Delhi may be asked to give their employees soft loans for the purchase of E-motor cars/Two-wheeler at much concessional interest rates.
- IV. Economic zones should be created at the outskirts of the city and wholesale business operators should be asked to create their warehouses/ commercial centers in these economic zones and all inter-state sales from Delhi city should be permitted from these economic zones only. This will streamline daily sales to various bordering states of Delhi and will reduce unnecessary influx of vehicles/ traders in the city on routine basis.
- V. Congestion charge should be levied on private motorcars entering congested zones during peak hours so that it works as a deterrent for those who make non emergent / repeated trips to these areas during peak hours. Simultaneously these commuters can be encouraged to perform their journeys by using public transport during non-peak hours by offering highly concessional rates.
- VI. National Capital Region Planning Board (NCRPB) has recently approved the draft regional plan 2041 according to which the NCR is likely to reduction in Size and shall be restricted within 100kms radius from Rajghat (Delhi) as a core area. It has also set an agenda of Slum free NCR, Heli taxi, 30 minute Mass Transit Rail System(MTRS) from NCR boundaries to Delhi. We can bring in further reforms to trigger exodus of people from congested areas of Delhi to the NCR townships such as Noida, Greater Noida, Sonapat, Ghaziabad, Faridabad, Bahadurgarh where a large number of flats & plots of all sizes are available at much lower rates as compared to Delhi. In this context following policy decisions may prove very helpful :-
 - i. Integration of rail road transport network of the NCR region and introduction of common travel pass for the entire region.
 - ii. Easy access to standard Medical, banking & educational facilities
 - iii. Single education Board for whole of the NCR REGION
 - iv. Integrated Traffic management & Civic services for entire NCR region
 - v. Concessional Property Registration & maintenance charges
 - vi. Declaration of NCR ZONE as a single entity for employees allowances
 - vii. As we know lacs of Two, Three or Four wheeler are used as carriers by various online supply chains & goods carriers for household services operations in Delhi city. These registered companies may be asked to use only E –vehicles for these supply operations and this may be declared the norm for all future registration of online suppliers & carriers.
 - viii. We may use AI services to integrate already available transport options in the city to enable commuters to have prior assessment of all travel options such as alternative modes of transport ,routes, travel schedules and charges enabling users to select routes and travel modes in the most economic and efficient manner.

The scholar conclude this review work with a note that no process can be successfully completed until and unless all the stakeholder work for the same with the same zeal and commitment. It is therefore important that residents of Delhi actively involve themselves and participate in various projects being launched by the Government Authorities /Civic bodies for reversing environmental degenerations discussed above as they are going to severely affect our present as well as future generations.

Conclusion

The above research work highlighted circumstances leading to concentration of a large number of people in Delhi City year after year and rapid urbanization along with growth in economic activities in the surrounding areas turning Delhi into one of the worst polluted & congested Metro City of India.

It also discuss in detail measures being taken by the Government of India as well as the State Government of Delhi(GNCTD)to arrest and control this environmental deterioration in and around the Metropolis.

The research work focus on the prevailing environmental conditions analyze Government Reforms & Policy measures targeting speedy reversal of these environmental degenerations faced by the City.

The scholar suggest following sort term & long term measures which according to him can speed up reforms:-

- a. Government should laydown norms for running of zonal head offices/Zonal Offices of PSUs including banks and educational institutions in Delhi.
- b. Hiring of Diesel, petrol & CNG driven cars by the Government Offices, PSUs, banks and educational institutions should be completely banned.
- c. All government establishments, banks and other education institutions in Delhi may be asked to give their employees low interest rate loans for the purchase of E-vehicles.
- d. Economic zones should be created at the outskirts of the city and wholesale businesses should be permitted from these economic zones only.
- e. Congestion charge should be levied on private motorcars entering congested zones during peak hours.
- f. Measures such as transport network integration; Common travel pass ; easy access to standard Medical, banking & educational facilities; single education Board ; well integrated Traffic management & Civic services; concessional property registration & maintenance charges for the entire NCR Region may prove to be highly tempting for the people of congested Delhi areas to migrate to environment friendly NCR zones.
- g. Compulsion of E-vehicles for companies running online business model
- h. Use of AI services for the integration of available transport options to enable commuters to
- i. make prior assessment of travel options and alternative routes and travel charges.

References:

Draft Regional Plan 2024: NCR -- News by DRISTI

Study on population, economy and employment for Delhi MPD 2041-final report sponsored by National Institute of Urban Affairs, New Delhi.

Economic survey of Delhi 2018-19

Economic survey of Delhi 2023-24

International Journal for Research Publications & Seminars, ISSN 2278-6848 volume 12 issue 02, April-June2021.

Article "Internal Migration –Issues prevailing in the NCT (National Capital Territory) of Delhi" by Anuja Sharma Saini, Ph.D. Scholar & A.M. Jose, Professor, Amity School of Economics -Amity University, Haryana. Spatial and Demographic growth of Delhi since 1947 and the main migration flows by VERONIQUE DVPONT.

OIZOM- Construction pollution impact of urban Development – Article by Kruti Davda.

Times of India news dated 9/10/2024

Times of India news dated 30/10/2024

Times of India news dated 2/11/2024

Times of India news dated 6/11/2024

Times of India news dated 7/11/2024

Times of India news dated 14/11/2024

Times of India news dated 26/11/2024

Times of India news dated 28/11/2024

Times of India news dated 20/12/2024

Times of India news dated 02/01/2025
Times of India news dated 07/01/2025
Times of India news dated 30/01/2025
Times of India news dated 7/02/2025
Times of India news dated 11/02/2025
Times of India news dated 09/03/2025
Times of India news dated 12/03/2025
Times of India news dated 14/03/2025
Times of India news dated 26/03/2025
Times of India news dated 08/04/2025
Times of India news dated 23/04/2025
Times of India news dated 23/04/2025
Times of India news dated 15/05/2025
Times of India news dated 29/08/2025
Times of India news dated 30/10/2025
Times of India news dated 6/11/2025
Times of India news dated 16/12/2025
Times of India news dated 24/12/2025
Times of India news dated 25/12/2025
Times of India news dated 1/01/2026
Times of India news dated 11/01/2026
Times of India news dated 31/01/2026
Times of India news dated 5/02/2026
Times of India news dated 7/02/2026
Times of India news dated 16/02/2026
Times of India news dated 7/03/2026
Times of India news dated 13/03/2026
Google search dated 14/11/2024
Google search dated 26/11/2024
Google search dated 6/02/2025
Google search dated 31/03/2025
Google search dated 06/05/2025
Google search dated 09/05/2025
Google search dated 12/03/2026